

**Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator: A Web-Based Tool for Quantifying Emissions
in Analytical Chemistry Laboratories**

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Abstract

The environmental impact of analytical chemistry laboratories—driven by chemical consumption, energy-demanding instrumentation, and single-use materials—represents a significant sustainability concern. To address this, the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) was developed as a free, web-based tool that quantitatively estimates the carbon footprint (CF) of analytical experiments. The calculator computes emissions from three primary contributors—chemical usage, energy consumption, and disposables—based on user-supplied activity data and emission factors. Three representative analytical methods were evaluated, showing that energy consumption is the dominant source of emissions, followed by disposable waste and reagents. Comparison with existing sustainability metrics (GAPI, NEMI, AGREE, WAC/BAGI, and CaFRI) highlights that, unlike qualitative or score-based tools, the ECF Calculator provides a quantitative, experiment-specific output in grams or kilograms of CO₂ equivalent. Although current calculations mainly cover Scopes 1–2 emissions, ECF calculator establishes a transparent framework that can be expanded to include broader life-cycle components. The ECF Calculator thus serves both as a practical and educational platform for promoting sustainable laboratory practices. It is freely accessible at www.ecfcalculator.com.

Keywords: Carbon footprint, Green metric, Green analytical chemistry, Laboratory tools.

1. Introduction

Over recent decades, the scientific discourse on anthropogenic climate change has intensified, with a broad consensus emerging on the substantial environmental and socio-economic impacts of increasing global temperatures [1,2]. The persistent rise in greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations, primarily driven by industrialization, energy consumption, and land-use changes, has been recognized as a major contributor to global warming [3]. Within this context, the concept of the carbon footprint (CF) has gained significant importance as a quantitative indicator for assessing the environmental burden of human activities [4]. CF represents the cumulative amount of GHG emissions, both direct and indirect, generated throughout a defined system boundary and expressed in carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e) [5]. By converting multiple emission sources into a single standardized metric, it provides a practical means to evaluate and compare environmental impacts across various sectors and activities [6].

Accurate quantification of the CF is fundamental to understanding the scale and distribution of greenhouse gas emissions arising from human activities [7]. By systematically accounting for both direct and indirect emission sources, CF assessment enables the identification of critical emission hotspots and supports the formulation of targeted mitigation strategies [8]. This quantitative framework is widely employed by policy-makers, industries, and institutions to evaluate environmental performance, align with international climate goals, and monitor progress toward decarbonization [9]. Reliable CF estimation not only facilitates evidence-based decision-making but also promotes transparency and accountability within sustainability initiatives [10]. Moreover, it provides a unified metric that bridges scientific analysis and practical implementation, guiding actions aimed at reducing environmental impact and improving overall resource efficiency.

Analytical chemistry laboratories, while essential for scientific progress, represent a major yet often overlooked source of greenhouse gas emissions. Recent assessments reveal that laboratory operations can emit between 4–6 t CO_{2e} per person annually, primarily due to high material consumption, intensive energy use, and ventilation demands [11]. A large-scale study across 108 European research facilities found that purchases and equipment-related activities account for over 50% of total laboratory emissions, surpassing electricity use and travel combined [12]. Moreover, analytical instruments such as HPLC, GC–MS, and ICP–OES operate continuously and require climate-controlled environments, consuming thousands of kilowatt-hours annually per unit [13]. Ventilation systems further exacerbate this energy burden—one standard chemical fume hood can consume energy equivalent to 3–3.5 average households per year [14]. Compounding this impact, laboratories worldwide generate an estimated 5.5 million metric tons of plastic waste annually, largely from single-use pipette tips, tubes, and gloves [15]. These findings collectively underscore the urgent need to integrate green chemistry principles into laboratory management, emphasizing solvent reduction, micro-scale analytical methods, and energy-efficient instrumentation as practical strategies for minimizing the carbon footprint of analytical science [14].

In recent years, the concept of low-carbon laboratories has gained significant attention as a transformative approach for minimizing the environmental footprint of scientific research without compromising analytical performance [16]. Such laboratories integrate energy-efficient instrumentation, digital monitoring of resource consumption, and sustainable waste management to achieve measurable reductions in carbon emissions. Transitioning toward microscale or solvent-free analytical methodologies has proven particularly effective, as these approaches substantially reduce chemical consumption and hazardous waste generation [17]. Likewise, replacing conventional devices with high-efficiency chromatographs, spectrometers, and cooling systems

can cut laboratory energy demand by up to 40–60% [18]. Optimized ventilation technologies, including variable air volume (VAV) fume hoods, further lower electricity usage by nearly 70% compared to constant air volume systems [19]. Another critical dimension involves material substitution, where shifting from single-use plastics to reusable or biodegradable alternatives markedly decreases laboratory waste streams [20]. Moreover, coupling such operational improvements with renewable energy integration—for instance, through solar-assisted power supply or localized energy recovery systems—fosters the development of climate-resilient research facilities. The emergence of low-carbon laboratories not only reflects a growing commitment to environmental responsibility but also aligns with the evolution of green analytical chemistry, in which quantitative sustainability metrics and assessment tools are increasingly employed to evaluate the greenness of analytical procedures.

Over the last decade, several complementary frameworks have been proposed to quantify the “greenness” or broader sustainability of analytical methods. GAPI introduced a holistic, procedure-wide pictogram that scores greenness from sampling to determination, expanding early pictogram ideas such as NEMI beyond a few hazard/solvent criteria [21,22]. AGREE then mapped the 12 principles of Green Analytical Chemistry onto a unified 0–1 metric with freely available software, enabling standardized, comparator-friendly assessments [23]. Moving past “green only,” the White Analytical Chemistry (WAC) paradigm integrated environmental (“green”), analytical performance (“red”), and practicality (“blue”) dimensions into a single “RGB” perspective, a direction that later motivated BAGI to quantify the blue/practicality component with a dedicated index and tool [24,25]. Most recently, CaFRI targeted a gap left by greenness-centric metrics by explicitly estimating and benchmarking the carbon footprint of laboratory procedures via a web tool designed to test reduction strategies [26].

In this study, the carbon footprint associated with analytical chemistry laboratories is addressed as a significant sustainability challenge. To support emission reduction efforts, a specialized software tool—Experimental Carbon Footprint (ECF) Calculator—was developed to quantify the environmental impact of analytical procedures. Unlike existing green assessment frameworks that provide qualitative or semi-quantitative sustainability scores, the ECF Calculator offers direct numerical estimation of carbon emissions (g CO_{2e}) arising from chemical use, energy consumption, and single-use materials. The tool is designed as a user-friendly and accessible platform for researchers who seek to evaluate and minimize laboratory emissions without requiring prior expertise in life-cycle assessment. By providing immediate, method-specific feedback during experimental design, the ECF Calculator bridges the gap between sustainability theory and practical laboratory application, thereby fostering a measurable, data-driven approach to greener analytical chemistry.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design and Working Principle of Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator

Analytical chemistry experiments inherently produce carbon emissions due to the combined effects of chemical usage, electricity demand, and the extensive reliance on disposable laboratory materials. To systematically evaluate these contributions, the Experimental Carbon Footprint (ECF) Calculator was designed to classify and quantify emission sources across three fundamental categories: chemical consumption, energy-intensive instrumentation, and single-use materials. This modular structure allows the tool to capture the full scope of laboratory-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions while maintaining transparency in data interpretation. For each category, the total carbon footprint (CF) is determined by multiplying the relevant activity data by its corresponding emission factor, following the general equation [27]:

Carbon Emissions (g CO₂e) = Activity Data (AD) × Emission Factor (EF)

This standardized approach ensures methodological consistency across diverse experimental setups and facilitates comparative evaluation between different analytical practices.

2.1.1. Chemicals

Chemical consumption constitutes a primary source of carbon emissions in analytical laboratories, as many reagents and solvents originate from energy-intensive, petroleum-based production processes. The manufacturing and purification of high-grade chemicals release significant amounts of greenhouse gases (GHGs), primarily carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), thereby contributing to the overall carbon footprint of laboratory operations [28]. Within the ECF Calculator, chemical-related emissions are computed using a mass-based approach, in which the quantity of each reagent (g) is multiplied by its respective emission factor (g CO₂e per g chemical). For liquid reagents, the entered volume data are internally converted to mass units using the corresponding density values and proper data, ensuring that all calculations are standardized on a gram basis. This calculation provides a direct numerical estimate of emissions associated with chemical consumption, enabling researchers to identify high-impact substances and prioritize greener alternatives. The tool's modular structure allows users to evaluate individual reagents or compare multiple chemicals within a single analytical procedure. The resulting values are subsequently integrated with other emission categories—energy use and disposables—to obtain the total laboratory carbon footprint, as illustrated in Figure 1.

2.1.2. Energy Consumption

Energy usage constitutes a major contributor to the overall carbon footprint of analytical laboratories, as most analytical instruments require continuous electrical input to ensure accuracy,

stability, and operational reliability. Within the ECF Calculator, energy-related emissions are estimated based on the hourly power consumption (kWh) of commonly used laboratory instruments, including spectrometers, chromatographs, centrifuges, and temperature-control devices. For user convenience, operational time is entered in minutes on input screen, which the program automatically converts into hours to ensure consistency in energy-based carbon footprint calculations. Average energy consumption values were compiled from manufacturer technical data and literature sources to represent typical laboratory conditions. The total energy demand for each device was obtained by multiplying its operational time by the corresponding power rating, and the resulting total electricity usage was converted to carbon dioxide equivalents (g CO₂e) using standardized emission factors for grid electricity. This module enables users to identify high-energy-demand equipment and to evaluate potential emission reductions through improved operational efficiency or transition to renewable power sources. The overall calculation workflow for this category is represented in Figure 1.

2.1.3. Laboratory Disposables

Single-use laboratory materials represent a major contributor to laboratory-related carbon emissions, primarily due to their production from fossil-derived polymers and their limited recyclability. In the ECF Calculator, the carbon footprint of disposable items—such as syringes, centrifuge tubes, pipette tips, and gloves—is determined by linking two main parameters: the raw material composition and the mass of the item. Average weights (in kilograms) of common disposables were compiled from manufacturer specifications, and each was multiplied by the corresponding material-specific emission factor (kg CO₂e per kg). This mass-based approach allows the tool to estimate emissions directly associated with the material's production phase. To account for the additional carbon burden from sterilization during production, a correction

coefficient of 1.2 was applied to items typically sterilized prior to packaging. The correction coefficient of 1.2 based on literature data describing the energy and carbon intensity of autoclaving and similar processes [29]. Although certain glass items could theoretically be reused, the ECF Calculator conservatively assumes single-use disposal after each experiment to standardize comparisons across laboratories. In practice, users only need to input the number of disposable items used, while the program automatically retrieves the default mass and emission factor of each material and computes the corresponding total CO₂e value. For example, a polypropylene syringe (0.007 kg; EF = 1.5 kg CO₂e/kg) results in approximately 12.6 g CO₂e per item, whereas a glass syringe—being heavier and requiring sterilization during production—emits around 73.8 g CO₂e. This design highlights how both the material origin and sterilization process critically influence the carbon footprint of disposables, reinforcing the importance of substituting high-impact single-use materials with reusable or low-emission alternatives whenever possible.

2.1.4. Total Carbon Footprint

The total carbon footprint of each analytical procedure was obtained by summing the emissions derived from the three main categories—chemical consumption, energy use, and disposable materials. Each module contributes independently to the overall calculation, allowing users to identify dominant emission sources within a given experiment. The final output is expressed in grams or kilograms of CO₂ equivalent (g or kg CO₂e), providing a standardized metric for comparing different laboratory activities. A schematic overview of this integrated calculation process is presented in Figure 1, illustrating the contribution of each subcategory to the total laboratory carbon footprint.

Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator ①

Usage Information: Follow these steps to calculate usage:

- **Step 1:** Enter the grams of chemicals used for each item.
- **Step 2:** Enter the usage minutes of each device.
- **Step 3:** Enter the quantity of disposables used.
- **User note:** Please make sure to select the checkbox after entering each input. The calculation will not run if the box is not selected.

Step 2: Select Devices ③

- Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
- UV-Vis Spectrophotometer
- Refrigerator
- Vortex mixer
- Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
- High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
- Gas Chromatography
- X-Ray Fluorescence
- Scanning Electron Microscope
- pH Meter

Usage (minutes): 2, 2, 20

Step 1: Select Chemicals ②

- Hydrochloric acid (HCl) 9 Grams
- Sulfuric acid (H2SO4) Grams
- Nitric acid (HNO3) Grams
- Acetic acid (C2H4O2) Grams
- Phosphoric acid (H3PO4) Grams
- Boric acid (H3BO3) Grams
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 10 Grams
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH) Grams
- Ammonium hydroxide (NH4OH) Grams
- Calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)2) Grams

Step 3: Select Disposables ④

- Syringe (glass) Quantity
- Syringe (plastic) 1
- UV-cuvette Quantity
- Pasteur pipette Quantity
- Micropipette Tip Quantity
- Centrifuge Tubes Quantity
- Disposable Funnels 2
- Weighing Boats or Weighing Paper Quantity
- Single-Use Pipettes 6
- Filtration Membranes Quantity

Result: ⑤

Total Carbon Footprint: 678.01 grams CO₂ (0.6780 kg CO₂)

Figure 1. Workflow of the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator, illustrating the sequential input process (chemicals, devices, disposables) and the resulting total carbon footprint output (in g CO₂ and kg CO₂).

2.2. Emission Factors

Emission factors (EFs) used in the ECF Calculator were compiled from multiple internationally recognized life-cycle assessment (LCA) databases and peer-reviewed literature to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Primary references include publicly available datasets from the U.S. EPA Greenhouse Gas Emission Factors Hub and other peer-reviewed literature values related to laboratory chemicals, energy use, and single-use plastics [30]. All emission factors are expressed as grams of CO₂ equivalent per functional unit—that is, g CO₂e per g for chemicals, g CO₂e per kWh for electricity consumption, and g CO₂e per item for disposables. Where multiple data sources

were available, averaged or median values were selected to reduce dataset bias. Energy-related factors were standardized using regional grid-mix averages ($400 \text{ g CO}_2\text{e kWh}^{-1}$) consistent with recent laboratory decarbonization assessments [31]. This harmonized dataset allows consistent calculation of the carbon footprint across all laboratory operations modeled in the ECF Calculator.

2.3. Software

The Experimental Carbon Footprint (ECF) Calculator was developed as a free, browser-based application designed to estimate the carbon footprint of analytical chemistry experiments. The program was built using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, featuring a clean multi-step interface that guides users through three main input categories: chemical usage, energy consumption, and disposable materials. All calculations are executed client-side, ensuring immediate feedback and full data privacy since no external database or server interaction is required. The tool integrates predefined emission factor datasets for each category, allowing users to calculate total CO_2 emissions in grams or kilograms of CO_2 equivalent (CO_2e). Its intuitive structure and accessible web deployment make it suitable for use by researchers, students, and laboratory personnel without requiring prior experience in environmental modelling or coding. The calculator is freely available online at www.ecfcalculator.com.

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation of Analytical Methods Using the ECF Calculator

To evaluate the performance and applicability of the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator), three representative analytical procedures were selected: (1) ionic liquid-based solidified floating organic drop microextraction (IL-SFODME) for lead determination by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS), (2) dispersive liquid–liquid

microextraction coupled with slotted quartz tube flame atomic absorption spectrometry (DLLME-SQT-FAAS) for copper analysis, and (3) a green liquid-phase microextraction (LPME) method employing nonanoic acid for the spectrophotometric determination of Rhodamine B [32-34]. These three procedures were chosen because they all represent microextraction-based analytical techniques, sharing similar experimental workflows while differing in chemical composition, operational energy demand, and disposable material use. This design enables a consistent yet comprehensive evaluation of the calculator's performance across comparable analytical configurations. For each method, the carbon footprint (CF) was computed using updated emission factors for three categories—chemical usage ($\text{g CO}_2\text{e g}^{-1}$ chemical), energy consumption ($\text{g CO}_2\text{e kWh}^{-1}$), and single-use materials ($\text{g CO}_2\text{e item}^{-1}$). All relevant input data (chemical amounts, device operation times, and disposable quantities) were entered into the ECF Calculator, yielding total CF values ranged between approximately 100 $\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$ and 400 $\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$ per experiment. Across all three cases, energy consumption from analytical instruments was identified as the dominant contributor, followed by emissions from disposable materials and chemical reagents. Although the selected methods share highly similar microextraction workflows, the ECF Calculator demonstrated sufficient sensitivity to detect variations in total emissions arising from differences in chemical type, solvent volume, and device operation time. This trend highlights the pivotal role of energy efficiency and waste reduction in minimizing laboratory-related emissions. A concise summary of the calculated results is presented in Table 1, where the relative contribution of each category to total emissions is also illustrated.

To provide further insight into the internal emission structure, Table 2 presents the detailed carbon footprint breakdown for Method 1, including the individual contributions of each reagent, device, and disposable item. This representation exemplifies the ECF Calculator's capability to quantify

and visualize emission sources at the component level, thereby supporting more targeted sustainability improvements in laboratory workflows.

Table 1. Summary of total carbon footprint results for three analytical methods calculated using the ECF Calculator.

	Method 1 [34]	Method 2 [35]	Method 3 [36]
Chemicals (g CO₂e)	4.62	31.38	5.99
Energy Consumption (g CO₂e)	253.35	204.97	21.08
Disposables (g CO₂e)	31.11	125.94	67.39
Total CF (g CO₂e)	289.08	362.29	94.46

Table 2. Detailed emission breakdown for Method 1.

Method 1 [34]			
	Chemical	Amount (gr)	Carbon Emission (g CO ₂ e)
Chemicals	1- dodecanol	0.075	0.19
	HMIM PF ₆	0.01	0.18
	Ethanol	0.175	0.07
	Magnesium Nitrate	1	1.3
	Potassium hydroge phthalate	0.5	2.5
	Hydrochloric acid	0.5	0.38
		Chemicals Total	4.62
	Energy Consumption	Device	Usage (min)
Magnetic stirrer		15	0.85
Refrigator		10	18.7
GFAAS		5	233.8
		Energy Consumption Total	253.35
Disposables	Disposable	Quantity	Carbon Emission (g CO ₂ e)
	Micropipette tip	2	0.9
	Pasteur pipette	1	8.61
	Centrifuge tube	1	21.6
		Disposables Total	31.11

3.2. Evaluation of Analytical Methods Using the ECF Calculator

Existing green analytical chemistry tools such as GAPI, NEMI, AGREE, White Analytical Chemistry (WAC), BAGI, and CaFRI mainly provide qualitative or score-based evaluations of method sustainability [21-26]. While they effectively highlight solvent toxicity, waste generation, or overall “greenness,” they lack the ability to quantify greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in absolute terms. In contrast, the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) offers a quantitative assessment by directly calculating emissions (g CO_{2e} or kg CO_{2e}) for a specific experiment. It integrates three measurable contributors—chemical usage, instrument energy consumption, and disposable materials—yielding a clear numerical footprint rather than a color or score. This quantitative, experiment-specific approach distinguishes the ECF Calculator from traditional greenness metrics, enabling direct comparison across laboratory operations and supporting both environmental reporting and method optimization. A concise comparison of these tools is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of sustainability assessment tools used in analytical chemistry.

Tool / Framework	Output type	Primary focus	Quantifies CO _{2e} directly?
NEMI [22]	Qualitative pictogram (yes/no flags)	Regulatory and environmental hazard of method steps	No
GAPI [21]	Color-coded multi-zone pictogram	Greenness of sampling, sample prep, reagents, waste	No
AGREE / AGREEprep [23]	0–1 numerical score + radial graphic	Compliance with 12 principles of green analytical chemistry	No
White Analytical Chemistry / RGB [24]	Multi-criterion “whiteness” profile	Balance of environmental impact, analytical performance, and practical feasibility	No (focus is multi-criteria balance)
BAGI (Blue Applicability Grade Index) [25]	Applicability/usability score (blue)	Practical feasibility, operator safety, cost, simplicity	No
CaFRI [26]	Reduction index / improvement score	Potential to decrease lab carbon footprint via alternatives	Partially (relative carbon impact, reduction potential)
ECF Calculator (this work)	Absolute mass of CO _{2e} (g / kg CO _{2e})	Experiment-specific carbon footprint from chemicals, energy use, and disposables	Yes (direct CO _{2e} output)

3.3. Limitations of ECF Calculator

Although the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) offers a straightforward and quantitative means to estimate emissions from laboratory-scale analytical experiments, several limitations should be acknowledged. The current version employs a single regional emission factor ($400 \text{ g CO}_2\text{e kWh}^{-1}$) for electricity consumption, which may not fully represent variations in national or institutional energy mixes. Likewise, user-entered input data—including reagent quantities, device operating times, and disposable counts—introduce uncertainty due to procedural variability or human error. In its present form, the calculator primarily accounts for direct (Scope 1) and indirect (Scope 2) emissions, whereas upstream and downstream impacts (Scope 3)—such as reagent synthesis, packaging, transport, and waste treatment—are not comprehensively included. The current framework, however, is designed to be flexible and adaptable, allowing future integration of additional sustainability indicators such as chemical toxicity, solvent hazard, or waste classification as complementary modules. This adaptability ensures that the ECF Calculator can evolve beyond carbon quantification toward a broader environmental assessment framework. As such, the reported footprints should be interpreted as minimum estimates of the true carbon burden while recognizing the tool's potential for expanded multi-criteria evaluation in subsequent versions.

Future developments could address these limitations by integrating region-specific electricity datasets, expanding the emission factor library to include life-cycle-based Scope 3 components, and automating data collection through digital laboratory logs. Beyond research applications, the ECF Calculator holds promise as an educational and decision-support tool, fostering carbon awareness among students and researchers while guiding greener laboratory practices.

4. Discussion

The integration of carbon awareness into analytical chemistry has become increasingly critical, as the discipline—traditionally focused on precision and reproducibility—has often remained detached from its environmental footprint. Laboratory-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions arise from multiple sources that align with the three scopes defined by the Greenhouse Gas Protocol: Scope 1, encompassing direct emissions from chemical reactions and solvent volatilization; Scope 2, representing indirect emissions from energy consumption by analytical instruments and ventilation systems; and Scope 3, including emissions from the production, transportation, and disposal of chemicals and disposable materials [35]. By integrating these emission categories into a unified framework, the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) provides a structured approach to quantify the environmental burden of laboratory activities. The results obtained from ECF Calculator applications demonstrate that variability in input parameters—such as emission factors, electricity grid mix, and laboratory operating conditions—can influence total carbon footprint values on the order of 10–20%, consistent with uncertainty ranges reported in life cycle assessment studies [36]. This degree of uncertainty is consistent with the natural variability inherent to emission modeling and underscores the importance of transparent assumptions and data traceability. Despite such variability, the calculator delivers sufficiently robust estimations to guide decision-making and promote more sustainable laboratory practices.

Beyond its quantitative function, the ECF Calculator also serves as an educational and self-assessment tool that fosters environmental literacy among students and researchers. Its intuitive, web-based interface enables non-specialists to explore the relationship between experimental design and environmental impact, encouraging critical reflection on chemical consumption, energy

efficiency, and waste minimization. Incorporating this tool into academic curricula or laboratory management systems can therefore accelerate the cultural shift toward low-carbon scientific research. Future improvements may include the integration of dynamic emission databases, region-specific electricity factors, and automated life cycle inventory (LCI) linkages to enhance accuracy and global applicability. Ultimately, the ECF Calculator establishes a practical foundation for embedding sustainability metrics within routine analytical workflows—bridging the gap between scientific innovation and environmental responsibility.

5. Conclusions

This study presents the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) as freely accessible, web-based platform specifically designed to quantify the carbon footprint of analytical chemistry experiments. By categorizing emissions from chemical usage, energy-intensive instrumentation, and single-use materials, the tool enables a transparent and reproducible estimation of laboratory-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The case studies conducted using the ECF Calculator demonstrated its practicality in identifying emission hotspots and evaluating greener analytical alternatives, thereby supporting sustainability-oriented decision-making. When compared with existing greenness assessment tools such as GAPI, AGREE, NEMI, BAGI, CaFRI, and the White Analytical Chemistry approach, the ECF Calculator provides a unique perspective by offering direct numerical quantification of CO₂-equivalent emissions rather than qualitative scoring. While its results depend on the accuracy of emission factors and user input data, the calculator remains a valuable and educational instrument that bridges the gap between environmental awareness and analytical performance. Future development will focus on integrating more comprehensive emission databases, region-specific energy factors, and automation modules to enhance precision and expand its applicability across diverse laboratory

settings. While downstream (Scope 3) processes—such as reagent production, packaging, and waste management—were not fully addressed, the framework’s adaptable structure allows integration of additional sustainability metrics, including toxicity and solvent hazards. Consequently, the reported values represent minimum estimates, emphasizing the tool’s potential to evolve into a comprehensive environmental assessment platform.

6. References

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8. Data Availability Statement

No new experimental data were created or analyzed in this study. The data supporting the carbon footprint calculations discussed in this article are derived from publicly available emission factor databases and are fully integrated within the Experimental Carbon Footprint Calculator (ECF Calculator) platform.

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10. Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

11. Note to Users

Users who wish to use the web-based tool but are unable to find specific chemicals, instruments, or disposable laboratory materials in the current database are kindly encouraged to contact the corresponding author (Barış Yıldız, barisyildiz7@hacettepe.edu.tr). Additional emission factors can be rapidly identified and incorporated into the tool upon request. Such feedback will contribute significantly to improving the coverage, accuracy, and long-term development of the experimental carbon footprint calculator.